

Complexes of Co(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with 2-(2'-Pyridyl)imidazoline

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Complexes of M^{2+} metal ions with 2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazoline (Pyimz) of the formulae $[M(Pyimz)_2X_2]$, ($M = Cu^{2+}$, Cd^{2+} or Hg^{2+} and $X = Cl^-$ or Br^-); $[Cu(Pyimz)_2X_2]$, ($X = NCS^-$ or NO_2^-); $[Cu(Pyimz)_2X]X$, ($X = I^-$ or ClO_4^-); $[Co(Pyimz)_2(NCS)_2]$ and $[Co(Pyimz)_2](ClO_4)_2$, have been prepared and characterised by uv and ir spectral studies, magnetic susceptibility and electrical conductance measurements at room temperature.

2-(2'-Pyridyl)imidazoline (Pyimz) is a strong chelate molecule ($pK_a = 8.54$)¹ possessing donor sites similar to α, α' -bipyridyl ($pK_a = 4.33$)¹ and 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole ($pK_a = 3.44$)¹.

2-(2'-Pyridyl)imidazoline

2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzimidazole

The formation constants of Pyimz and 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole complexes with some metal ions in solution and the effect of coordination on the infrared spectral N-H and C=N vibrations of the ligand were reported by Walter *et al.*¹⁻³. We had earlier reported the structural aspects of complexes of 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole with a number of metal ions^{4,5}. We are now reporting the preparation and characterisation of the complexes of Co(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with Pyimz.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by the reported method³. The metal salts and chemicals used were of B. D. H. AnalaR grade or E. Merck extra pure grade.

Preparation of metal complexes :

$M(Pyimz)_2X_2$ [$M = Cu(II)$, $Cd(II)$ or $Hg(II)$; $X = Cl^-$ or Br^-]: An ethanolic solution of metal halide (0.01 mole in 40 ml) was refluxed with stoichiometric proportion of the ligand on a steam bath for about 20 min. From the refluxate, the dihalo complexes separated gradually either on standing or on concentrating and cooling at room temperature. The products were collected, washed with cold ethanol and dried *in vacuo* over $CaCl_2$.

$Cu(Pyimz)_2X_2$ ($X = NO_2^-$ or NCS^-): An aqueous ethanolic suspension of the dichloro complex, $Cu(Pyimz)_2Cl_2$, was refluxed on a steam bath for about 1 hr with excess of sodium or potassium salt

of appropriate anion, when the yellowish green dihalo complexes separated. The products were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried as above.

$Cu(Pyimz)_2X_2$ ($X = I^-$ or ClO_4^-): An aqueous ethanolic solution of copper(II) chloride was refluxed with stoichiometric proportion of the ligand for 0.5 hr. The resulting solution was concentrated and treated with an excess of saturated solution of KI or $NaClO_4$ when greenish blue compound separated gradually. The products were filtered, washed with cold water and dried as above.

$Co(Pyimz)_2(NCS)_2$: An ethanolic solution of cobalt(II) chloride was refluxed with the ligand in 1:2 molar proportion and the resulting solution was treated with an excess of saturated aqueous solution of potassium thiocyanate. Buff coloured precipitates separated slowly. The product was washed with ethanol and ether and dried *in vacuo*.

$Co(Pyimz)_2(ClO_4)_2$: The complex was obtained as a cream yellow precipitate when ethanolic solution of hydrated cobalt(II) perchlorate was refluxed with stoichiometric amount of the ligand and the resulting solution was treated with an excess of ethanolic solution of $NaClO_4$.

The analytical results, magnetic susceptibility values at room temperature and electrical conductance values of the complexes were determined as reported earlier⁴. The values are given in Table 1.

The magnetic moment values of the copper(II) complexes were calculated after making correction for T. I. P. contribution⁶. The solid reflectance spectra of the complexes were recorded on Hilger and Watts UV spectrophotometer model H-700 using $MgCO_3$ as standard. The ir spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 237 spectrophotometer as KBr disc. The prominent ir bands of the ligand and some complexes are recorded in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

The dihalo complexes, $M(Pyimz)_2X_2$ [$M = Cu(II)$, $Cd(II)$ or $Hg(II)$; $X = Cl^-$ or Br^-], are sparingly soluble

TABLE 1

Complex (colour)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	%Metal Found (Calcd.)	%Nitrogen Found (Calcd.)	%Halogen Found (Calcd.)	Molar conductance ($\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$)
Cd(Pyimz)Cl ₂ (White)	Dia	39.84 (34.01)	12.68 (12.71)	21.08 (21.48)	25
Cd(Pyimz)Br ₂ (Cream white)	Dia	27.07 (26.81)	9.82 (10.02)	38.84 (38.18)	26
Cu(Pyimz)Cl ₂ (Bright green)	1.78	22.31 (22.54)	15.01 (14.92)	24.96 (25.20)	20
Cu(Pyimz)Br ₂ (Brown)	1.81	16.88 (17.19)	11.42 (11.94)	42.81 (43.19)	22
Cu(Pyimz)(NCS) ₂ (Yellowish green)	1.86	19.21 (19.44)	21.68 (22.45)	—	18
Cu(Pyimz)(ONO) ₂ (Yellowish green)	1.82	21.12 (20.96)	22.88 (23.14)	—	—
Cu(Pyimz) ₂ I ₂ (Yellowish green)	1.92	10.21 (10.37)	13.61 (13.74)	40.96 (40.50)	81
Cu(Pyimz) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂ (Greenish blue)	1.88	11.26 (11.40)	14.91 (15.09)	—	95
Co(Pyimz) ₂ (NCS) ₂ (Buff)	4.92	12.32 (12.54)	23.58 (23.86)	—	—
Co(Pyimz) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂ (Cream)	5.02	8.81 (8.42)	17.89 (18.03)	—	148
Hg(Pyimz)Cl ₂ (White)	Dia	48.18 (47.94)	9.87 (10.03)	17.18 (16.95)	18
Hg(Pyimz)Br ₂ (White)	Dia	39.70 (39.54)	8.12 (8.28)	31.81 (31.51)	16

in water and ethanol but dissolve fairly in DMF or dioxane. The DMF solution of the complexes display very low electrical conductance value (16-28 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$) indicating that anions are coordinated in these complexes.

The molar electrical conductance value of $\text{Cu(Pyimz)}_2\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{I}^-$ or ClO_4^-) in DMF solution is found in the range of 85-95 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$ which fall in the range of 1:1 electrolyte⁷. It is thus inferred that one of the anion of $\text{Cu(Pyimz)}_2\text{X}_2$ is coordinated to metal atom and these complexes are pentacoordinated. The molar electrical conductance value of $\text{Co(Pyimz)}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (148 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$) fall in the range of that of 1:2 electrolyte⁷.

The magnetic moment value of cobalt(II) complexes occur in the range of 4.92-5.02 B.M. (Table 1), being similar to the value for high spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes⁸. The magnetic moment value of Cu(II) complexes are in the range of 1.78-1.92 B.M. indicating that the complexes are magnetically dilute^{8,9}. The diffused reflectance spectra of diacido complexes, $\text{Cu(Pyimz)}_2\text{X}_2$, display strong absorption near 23500-25600 cm^{-1} probably of charge transfer type and a broad and medium band between 12200 and 15600 cm^{-1} assignable to d-d transitions¹⁰. The bischelated complex, $\text{Cu(Pyimz)}_2\text{X}_2$, ($\text{X} = \text{I}^-$ or ClO_4^-) displays a medium and broad band near 15180-14280 cm^{-1} due to d-d transition¹⁰. The complex, $\text{Co(Pyimz)}_2(\text{NCS})_2$, displays a medium band at 18020 cm^{-1} and a shoulder at 22720 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions¹¹, respectively. The former band is generally weak but in the present complex it has gained intensity due to tetragonal distortion¹¹. The complex perchlorate, $\text{Co(Pyimz)}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, shows a weak

band at 22860 cm^{-1} and a shoulder near 19280 cm^{-1} due to d-d transitions in octahedral field (Table 2).

TABLE 2—DIFFUSED REFLECTANCE BAND POSITION (cm^{-1}) WITH THEIR PROBABLE ASSIGNMENTS

Complex	Band position (cm^{-1})	Assignments
$\text{Co(Pyimz)}_2(\text{NCS})_2$	18020 m	${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$
	22720 sh	${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$
$\text{Co(Pyimz)}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$	19280 sh	${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$
	22860 sh	${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$
Cu(Pyimz)Cl_2	25640 s	C-T
	13890-12200 m br	${}^2\text{T}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ (or ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g + {}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$)
Cu(Pyimz)Br_2	23570 m	C-T
	13890-12500 m br	${}^2\text{T}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$
Cu(Pyimz)(ONO)_2	24370 m	C-T
	15600 m	${}^2\text{T}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$
$\text{Cu(Pyimz)}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$	15180 m br	${}^2\text{T}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$
Cu(Pyimz)(NCS)_2	13890 m br	${}^2\text{T}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$
$\text{Cu(Pyimz)}_2\text{I}_2$	14280 m br	${}^2\text{T}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$

m = medium ; sh = shoulder ; s = strong and br = broad.

The ir spectrum of $\text{Cu(Pyimz)(NO}_2)_2$ exhibits $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1420 and 1362, $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1140 and $\delta(\text{ONO})$ at 825 cm^{-1} . The observed frequency of $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NO}_2)$ vibration falls in the range of oxygen bonded NO_2 group¹². The ir spectrum of Cu(Pyimz)(NCS)_2 displays a broad and very strong $\nu(\text{CN})$ band at 2100 and a weak $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ band at 820 cm^{-1} indicating the bonding of the NCS group through nitrogen atom¹². The ir spectrum of $\text{Co(Pyimz)}_2(\text{NCS})_2$ displays $\nu(\text{CN})$ band as a strong and broad band at 2085 and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ at 830 cm^{-1} which fall in the range of N-bonded thiocyanate group¹². The ir spectrum of $\text{Co(Pyimz)}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$

TABLE 3—PROMINENT IR BANDS IN cm^{-1}

Compound	$\nu(\text{NH})$	$\nu(\text{ON})$	$\nu(\text{C=N}) + (\text{C=O})$	$\delta(\text{NH})$	Pyridine ring breathing mode	Anion Bands
Pyimz	3328	1664	1595	1506	996	—
Cu(Pyimz)Cl ₂	3285	1628	1590	1512	1012	—
Cu(Pyimz) ₂ I ₂	3278	1634	1588	1516	1014	—
Cu(Pyimz) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	3302	1622	1590	1522	1008	1130 s br, 1072 m $\nu(\text{ClO})$
Cd(Pyimz)Cl ₂	3303	1634	1586	1510	1012	—
Hg(Pyimz)Cl ₂	3312	1628	1592	1515	1020	—
Co(Pyimz) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	3281	1631	1585	1520	1018	1122 s br $\nu(\text{ClO})$
Co(Pyimz) ₂ (NCS) ₂	3292	1627	1586	1518	1015	2085 s br, 830 w
Cu(Pyimz)(NCS) ₂	3296	1626	1590	1510	1020	2100 s br, 820 w
Cu(Pyimz)(ONO) ₂	3284	1624	1588	1508	1006	1420 s br, 1362 m, 1040 m, 832 w, 825 s

s=strong ; m=medium ; w=weak and br=broad.

displays a broad and strong band at 1122 cm^{-1} [$\nu_s(\text{ClO})$ asymmetric stretch] which, according to Underhill *et al*¹², is the characteristic band of ionic perchlorate group.

The (N-H) stretching band of the free ligand⁸ is observed at 3328 cm^{-1} which is shifted to lower frequencies by $20\text{-}50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in its complexes. The $\nu(\text{C=N})$ of imidazoline ring is observed at 1664 cm^{-1} which is also shifted to lower frequency and observed between 1623 and 1634 cm^{-1} . The pyridine ring $\nu(\text{C=N})$ vibration coupled with $\nu(\text{C=C})$ vibration of Pyimz is observed at 1595 cm^{-1} . In complexes, this band is shifted to lower frequency by $5\text{-}10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The shift of $\nu(\text{CN})$ vibration suggests the bonding of the ligand molecule through tertiary nitrogen atoms of imidazoline as well as the pyridine ring^{14,15}. The shift of $\nu(\text{NH})$ stretch of the ligand in complexes can be attributed to intermolecular association of complex molecules probably through NH hydrogen in solid state. The pyridine ring breathing mode of the ligand is observed at 996 cm^{-1} which is shifted to higher frequencies by $10\text{-}25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes and this has been taken to be the diagnostic of coordinated pyridine nitrogen in complexes⁸. The $\nu(\text{M-N})$ and $\nu(\text{M-X})$ vibrations in the complexes occur beyond the range of instrument.

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